

SCIENCE INVESTIGATORY PROJECTS IMPLEMENTATION: ADMINISTRATORS' SUPPORT, TEACHERS' COMPETENCE, AND STUDENTS' OUTCOMES

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects (SIPs) in selected public elementary schools, focusing on administrators' support, teachers' competence, and students' outcomes. A descriptive qualitative research design was employed to capture the experiences and practices of participants in their natural school settings. The study was conducted in six public elementary schools recognized as Top 3 winners in division-level SIP competitions in the Bohol and City Divisions during School Year 2025–2026. A total of 18 participants, composed of school administrators, science teachers, and student-researchers, were selected through purposive sampling. Data were gathered using a semi-structured interview guide and analyzed through thematic analysis. Findings revealed that administrators provided support through strategic direction, resource allocation, time management, monitoring, capacity building, and recognition systems. Teachers demonstrated key competencies in scaffolding the research process, applying research methods, coaching scientific communication, adapting to constraints, and learning through facilitation. These support mechanisms and competencies collectively influenced student outcomes, leading to improved confidence, enhanced critical thinking and inquiry skills, better research and communication abilities, and increased independence and motivation in conducting research. The study concludes that effective SIP implementation is achieved through the integration of strong administrative leadership, competent teacher facilitation, and active student engagement within a structured support system. It is recommended that schools institutionalize clear SIP guidelines, allocate sufficient resources, strengthen teacher professional

development, provide structured coaching opportunities, and sustain recognition mechanisms to enhance student participation and performance in science research.

Keywords: *Science Investigatory Projects, administrative support, teacher competence, student outcomes, qualitative research, science education*

INTRODUCTION

Science education plays a vital role in national development because it fosters innovation, strengthens problem-solving, improves public health awareness, and prepares communities to respond to emerging challenges such as climate change and disease outbreaks. In the Philippine basic education system, scientific literacy begins at the elementary level, where learners are introduced to foundational concepts and inquiry-based learning experiences. Early exposure to meaningful science activities helps develop curiosity, analytical thinking, and long-term academic growth.

One of the key school-based strategies that promotes inquiry and scientific thinking is the Science Investigatory Project (SIP). SIPs allow learners to identify problems, formulate questions, conduct experiments, analyze results, and communicate findings in a structured and creative way. In the Philippine context, SIPs have been reinforced through Department of Education initiatives and science-focused programs that aim to cultivate research culture, innovation, and critical thinking among learners. However, the successful implementation of SIPs does not depend on student participation alone. It also requires competent teachers who can mentor the research process and school administrators who can provide leadership, resources, and institutional support.

Teachers play a central role in guiding learners throughout the different stages of science investigatory work. Sanchez and Rosaroso (2019) emphasized that science teachers are crucial in the planning, conduct, and assessment of Science Investigatory Projects, directly influencing learner engagement and project success. Tejero (2025) likewise found that learners showed stronger ability to analyze, synthesize, and interpret scientific data when investigatory projects were meaningfully integrated into instruction. In a related way, Giaffredo et al. (2022) noted that project-based learning improved student engagement and competence when supported by structured pedagogy. These findings suggest that teacher competence is a major factor in helping learners successfully complete research-based science tasks.

At the same time, administrative support remains essential in sustaining school-based science research programs. Administrators help create conditions that allow SIPs to flourish through funding, scheduling, training support, provision of materials, recognition mechanisms, and instructional leadership. Manalo (2021), in examining Project i-CREATE, reported that strong school leadership and resource allocation improved student participation, enhanced research outputs, and increased school recognition in science-related activities. Pasaquian (2024) found that while teachers

demonstrated strong engagement in public elementary schools, challenges such as limited institutional support, workload demands, and insufficient resources affected the effective implementation of school-based programs, including research-related activities like Science Investigatory Projects. These studies show that strong teacher mentoring alone is not enough; supportive school structures are likewise necessary for sustained success.

Although previous studies have contributed important insights, much of the literature has examined student performance, teacher competence, or school support as separate concerns. Limited attention has been given to how administrators' support and teachers' competence work together in shaping student outcomes in Science Investigatory Projects, particularly in elementary schools and in rural or provincial settings. This gap is important because SIP implementation is influenced not only by individual teacher effort or student ability, but also by the broader support system within the school. In Bohol and nearby city divisions, where schools vary in resources, mentoring opportunities, and administrative capacity, understanding this interaction is necessary to strengthen research-based science education.

The present study addressed this gap by examining Science Investigatory Projects implementation in selected schools in the Bohol and City Divisions. It focused on three interrelated dimensions: administrators' support, teachers' competence, and students' outcomes. Specifically, it explored the forms of support provided by school administrators, the competencies and experiences demonstrated by science teachers in facilitating SIPs, and the ways these influenced students' proficiency and performance in developing Science Investigatory Projects. Based on the findings, the study also proposed a research management framework that may serve as a guide for strengthening SIP implementation in public elementary schools.

This study is anchored on theoretical perspectives that explain how professional growth, leadership support, and reflective practice contribute to educational improvement. Transformative Learning Theory explains that educators develop when they critically reflect on their assumptions and adjust their practices in response to new demands. In the context of SIP implementation, this is evident when teachers shift from traditional teaching approaches to inquiry-based facilitation and when administrators adopt more responsive ways of supporting research activities in schools. Adult Learning Theory further explains that teachers and school leaders learn best when professional development is relevant, practical, and directly connected to real school problems. Reflective Practice Theory also highlights the importance of continuous reflection in improving professional action, allowing teachers to refine their mentoring approaches and administrators to enhance the support systems needed for effective SIP implementation.

The study is likewise supported by broader policy directions that promote science education and research participation. International frameworks affirm the right of learners to participate in scientific advancement and benefit from its applications, while national educational mandates in the Philippines emphasize the promotion of science and

technology across all levels of education. These policy directions provide a strong basis for integrating Science Investigatory Projects into school practice and for examining the conditions that influence their implementation.

Overall, Science Investigatory Projects are important platforms for developing inquiry, creativity, problem-solving, and scientific thinking among learners. Their successful implementation depends on the interaction of competent teachers, supportive administrators, and school conditions that encourage research and innovation. By examining these interconnected factors, this study contributes to a clearer understanding of how SIP implementation can be strengthened and sustained in public elementary schools.

Research Questions

This study explored how administrators' support, teachers' competence, and students' outcomes collectively shaped the success of Science Investigatory Projects in Bohol and City Divisions for School Year 2025-2026.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What forms of support did school administrators provide in the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects?
2. What competencies and experiences did science teachers demonstrate in facilitating Science Investigatory Projects?
3. How did administrators' support and teachers' competence influence student outcomes in developing proficiency in Science Investigatory Projects?
4. What research management framework was proposed based on the findings?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive qualitative research design. This approach is appropriate for examining phenomena as experienced by participants in their natural settings and for presenting these experiences in clear, straightforward terms rather than in highly abstract theoretical language (Sandelowski, 2000; Doyle et al., 2020; Turale, 2020). It is particularly useful for studies that seek to understand what occurs and how it occurs within a specific context.

This design was suitable for the present study because it aimed to describe administrators' support, teachers' competence, and students' outcomes in the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects. Data were collected through interviews and document review from winning schools in the Bohol and City Divisions. The design enabled the researchers to capture the perspectives of administrators, teachers, and students and to identify themes that reflected the actual practices and experiences underlying SIP implementation in the school context.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in six public elementary schools recognized as Top 3 winners in the Sibol–Science Investigatory Project competitions at the division level during School Year 2025–2026. The research sites included three winning schools from the City Division and three from the Bohol Division, selected on a per-division basis to ensure representation from both contexts.

These schools were chosen because their performance reflected strong Science Investigatory Project implementation. As award-winning schools, they provided suitable settings for examining how administrators' support and teachers' competence influenced students' outcomes in SIP implementation.

Research Participants

The study involved 18 participants composed of school administrators, science teachers, and student-researchers from the City Division and Bohol Division. Specifically, the participants included six administrators, six science teachers, and six student-researchers. They were selected through purposive sampling based on their direct involvement in the planning, mentoring, and participation in Science Investigatory Projects during the covered school years.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

Area	Respondents (Top 3 Winning Schools)			Total
	Administrators	Science Teachers	Student Researcher	
Tagbilaran City Division	3	3	3	9
Bohol Division	3	3	3	9
Total	6	6	6	18

Research Instrument

The study used a semi-structured interview guide as the primary data-gathering instrument. The guide was aligned with the research questions and organized around three dimensions: administrators' support, teachers' competence, and students' outcomes in the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects. Separate but related questions were prepared for school administrators, science teachers, and student-researchers to capture their respective perspectives on SIP implementation.

To ensure content validity, the interview guide was reviewed by research advisers and experts in science education. Their comments were incorporated to improve the clarity and relevance of the questions. A pilot test was also conducted in a non-participating school to check the comprehensibility and sequencing of the items.

Research Procedure

Data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with school administrators, science teachers, and student-researchers from the selected schools in the City Division and Bohol Division. Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the concerned school authorities and participants. Interviews were conducted face-to-face at a convenient time and place within the school premises and were audio-recorded with the participants' consent for transcription purposes.

For student participants, parental consent and learner assent were obtained before the interviews. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained through the use of codes instead of names, and participation was strictly voluntary. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any point.

Data Analysis

The interview transcripts were analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke (2006, 2019). This method was used to identify and develop patterns of meaning across the data. The analysis followed six phases: familiarization with the data, generation of initial codes, construction of themes, review of themes, definition and naming of themes, and writing of the report.

Throughout the analysis, the researcher-maintained reflexivity by examining personal assumptions and their possible influence on interpretation. Trustworthiness was strengthened through member checking, triangulation of participant groups, and documentation of analytic decisions. These procedures helped ensure the credibility and dependability of the findings.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings on the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects in the Bohol and City Divisions during School Year 2025–2026. It focuses on the support provided by school administrators, the competence demonstrated by science teachers, and the student outcomes associated with SIP implementation.

Forms of Administrative Support in SIP Implementation

Analysis of the interview data generated six major themes describing the forms of support provided by school administrators in the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects (SIPs): (1) Strategic Direction and Policy-Guided Implementation, (2) Resource Provision and Funding Mobilization, (3) Time and Structural Support for Project Work, (4) Implementation Oversight, Monitoring, and Accountability, (5) Human Resource Deployment and Capacity Building, and (6) Motivational and Recognition Support for Participation and Performance. These themes show that SIP implementation is supported through deliberate administrative actions across policy, finance, scheduling, supervision, teacher development, and motivation. The findings indicate that administrative support operates through multiple coordinated practices rather than isolated efforts.

Theme 1: Strategic Direction and Policy-Guided Implementation

Administrators describe their support as providing direction and structured guidance for SIP implementation. One participant stated, “*I provide a clear direction on the SIP goals and objectives*” (JOHN, 50 years old, Principal I, Talibon 1 ES, Bohol Division). Another emphasized, “*Clear step-by-step guidelines for students and coach in choosing topics, conducting experiments, analyzing data and presenting result*” (JOSH, 55 years old, Principal, Mansasa ES, City Division). Ensuring compliance was also highlighted: “*Ensure the projects comply with the school policies*” (JOSH, 55 years old, Principal, Mansasa ES, City Division).

The data show that administrators frame support as setting expectations and defining procedures. The repeated references to “clear direction,” “guidelines,” and “compliance” suggest that SIP implementation is structured rather than informal. The emphasis lies on clarifying how SIP should be conducted and aligning it with school policies. The support here operates through direction-setting and procedural clarity.

This theme aligns with Manalo (2021), who reported that structured administrative direction strengthened the implementation of school-based science research programs. It also reflects DepEd Memorandum No. 068, s. 2023, which institutionalizes SIP within formal science education frameworks. Prior scholarship emphasizes that instructional leadership requires clear vision and structured guidance to sustain academic initiatives, especially research-based programs.

Theme 2: Resource Provision and Funding Mobilization

Financial and material support appears prominently in administrators’ accounts. One administrator stated, “*Provide financial resources from MOOE funds*” (LUCY, 51 years old, Principal, Manga ES, City Division). Another shared, “*Full allocation for the materials, equipment necessary for the experimentation*” (JOSH, 55 years old, Principal, Mansasa ES, City Division).

At the same time, financial constraints were acknowledged. One participant said, “Limited budget... prioritize essential needs” (MARIA, 54 years old, Principal I, Camambugan ES, Bohol Division). Another noted, “Insufficient funds – tapping the SPTA for support” (NINA, 58 years old, Principal, City Central ES, City Division).

These statements indicate that administrators perceive support as ensuring material availability while managing limitations. The explicit references to MOOE, budget prioritization, and stakeholder tapping show that financial decision-making is central to SIP support. The data consistently frame support as enabling experimentation through resource allocation.

Interestingly, Pasaquian (2024) emphasized the importance of institutional resource allocation in sustaining school-based initiatives. Similarly, UNESCO’s recommendations on science education emphasize the institutional responsibility to create enabling environments for research participation. Studies on science investigatory projects consistently identify access to materials and laboratory resources as a determinant of successful implementation.

Theme 3: Time and Structural Support for Project Work

Time allocation is described as another important form of support. One administrator explained, “Allocate time for students and coach during school hours and after school session” (JOSH, 55 years old, Principal, Mansasa ES, City Division). Another stated, “Time constraints – adjust schedules and assign coordinators to streamline processes” (JOHN, 50 years old, Principal I, Talibon 1 ES, Bohol Division).

These responses indicate that administrators recognize time constraints as a challenge and respond by adjusting schedules or formally allocating work time. The support provided is structural in nature. It involves reorganizing school routines to accommodate SIP activities. The data show that time is treated as a necessary condition for SIP completion.

Experiential learning theories emphasize the importance of structured time for inquiry and reflection. Tejero (2025) found that integrating SIP within regular school routines improved students’ science process skills. Research in inquiry-based education similarly underscores that without allocated time, project-based learning cannot be sustained effectively.

Theme 4: Implementation Oversight, Monitoring, and Accountability

Monitoring and oversight are directly mentioned as forms of support. One principal cited “Monitoring and accountability” (JOHN, 50 years old, Principal I, Talibon 1 ES, Bohol Division). Another described “Regular follow-ups of the study conducted in relation to SIP” (LUCY, 51 years old, Principal, Manga ES, City Division).

These statements demonstrate that administrators remain actively involved after initiation. Support includes tracking progress and ensuring that projects continue as planned. The data suggest that oversight functions as a mechanism for sustaining project movement and maintaining expected standards.

Sanchez and Rosaroso (2019) emphasized that structured supervision and guidance throughout the investigatory process influence student outcomes. Research on instructional leadership also identifies monitoring and feedback mechanisms as essential in ensuring fidelity of program implementation.

Theme 5: Human Resource Deployment and Capacity Building

Administrators highlight teacher involvement as central to SIP success. One participant stated, “Select competent and committed Science teacher that spearheads the SIP” (LUCY, 51 years old, Principal, Manga ES, City Division). Another shared, “Conducted targeted professional development mentoring and coaching to build confidence and skills” (JOHN, 50 years old, Principal I, Talibon 1 ES, Bohol Division).

These accounts indicate two approaches to support: selecting teachers perceived as capable and strengthening teachers through mentoring and coaching. The support provided focuses on ensuring that teachers are prepared to guide students. The data clearly associate SIP implementation with teacher competence, and administrators respond by managing and developing human resources.

Cai and Hong (2023) stressed the importance of enhancing teachers’ research-related competencies. Llano Jr. et al. (2023) also found that teachers’ facilitating strategies significantly shape SIP implementation. These studies affirm that teacher capacity development is central to sustaining inquiry-based programs.

Theme 6: Motivational and Recognition Support for Participation and Performance

Administrators also describe providing encouragement and recognition. One principal mentioned “*Financial and moral support*” (NINA, 58 years old, Principal, City Central ES, City Division). Another stated, “Approved best SIP to represent in the division level competition” (Proserpina A. Doroy, School Principal, Manga ES, City Division).

These responses show that support includes affirming efforts and creating opportunities for representation in competitions. Recognition appears to function as motivation for both teachers and students. The data indicate that administrators not only facilitate project completion but also promote visibility and performance through contests and representation.

Manalo (2021) found that recognition and administrative encouragement enhanced student engagement and school research culture. Research on school motivation systems also suggests that public recognition and performance opportunities contribute to sustained participation in academic programs.

Moreover, across both divisions, administrators provide support through six identifiable practices: giving direction and guidelines, allocating funds and materials, restructuring schedules, monitoring progress, managing teacher competence, and offering recognition and encouragement. Each theme is directly grounded in participants' explicit descriptions of what they do to support SIP implementation. The patterns reflect layered administrative involvement that combines structural, financial, supervisory, human resource, and motivational actions.

The six forms of support identified in this study are also supported by previous research on school-based science programs. Manalo (2021) found that research initiatives in schools become stronger when administrators actively provide resources, organize the process clearly, and recognize the efforts of teachers and students. In the same way, Sanchez and Rosaroso (2019) emphasized that Science Investigatory Projects succeed when there is consistent guidance and supervision from school leaders throughout the different stages of the project. These studies support the idea that SIP implementation improves when administrators are involved not only in funding but also in guiding, monitoring, and encouraging the whole process.

Teachers' Competencies in SIP Facilitation

The analysis of the transcript generated five themes that describe the competencies and experiences of science teachers in facilitating Science Investigatory Projects: (1) Scaffolding the Research Process, (2) Demonstrating Research Method Competence, (3) Coaching Scientific Communication, (4) Adapting to Time and Resource Constraints, and (5) Learning Through Facilitation Experience.

Theme 1: Scaffolding the Research Process

Teachers describe their competence as guiding students carefully through each stage of the investigatory process. One teacher shared, *"At first, many students were unsure how to begin... I helped the students follow the process"* (JOSEPH, 30 years old, Teacher I, Talibon 1 ES, Bohol Division). Another explained, *"I guide them step by step so they don't feel overwhelmed... broke task into manageable steps"* (MARYJANE, 29 years old, Teacher I, Camambugan ES, Bohol Division). A City Division teacher also stated, *"I use scaffolding techniques... breaking down the task into small manageable steps"* (JEAN, 28 years old, Teacher I, Mansasa ES, City Division).

These statements show that teachers focus on making research manageable for young learners. Students often struggle at the beginning. Teachers respond by dividing tasks into smaller parts and guiding them through each phase. They select topics suited to the learners' level and help them move step by step. This reflects practical classroom skill rather than abstract theory.

This finding aligns with Llano Jr. et al. (2023), who explained that structured guidance strengthens student engagement in investigatory projects. Similarly, Cai and Hong (2023) emphasized that teachers need to translate complex research tasks into

simpler steps that learners can handle. The teachers in this study describe exactly that kind of structured support.

Theme 2: Demonstrating Research Method Competence

Teachers also show competence in handling research procedures. One teacher explained how he guided students in *“shaping it into a clear research question”* (JOSEPH, 30 years old, Teacher I, Talibon 1 ES, Bohol Division). He further described using *“knowledge in experimental design... treatments (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%)”*. Another teacher mentioned teaching students how to use tables *“so patterns could be seen easily.”* A City Division teacher added that she guides students in using graphs and reviewing their methods carefully (ANNE, 30 years old, Teacher III, City Central ES, City Division).

These responses show that teachers apply research knowledge directly in class. They help students frame clear questions, structure experiments, organize findings, and explain results. They guide learners in understanding how evidence works and how it should be presented.

This theme is supported by Sanchez and Rosaroso (2019), who noted that teachers' methodological knowledge influences the quality of SIP outputs. In the same way, Tejero (2025) found that students' science skills improve when teachers provide direct instruction in data organization and interpretation. The teachers in this study demonstrate these competencies in their descriptions.

Theme 3: Coaching Scientific Communication

Teachers describe how they prepare students to present and defend their work. One teacher shared, *“Balik-balik... possible question... na unlock ilang confidence”* (MARY, 27 years old, Teacher I, Larapan ES, Bohol Division). Another said, *“Communication... important in presenting”* (JEAN, 28 years old, Teacher I, Mansasa ES, City Division). A City Central teacher explained that she conducts *“structured mentorship through regular meetings and staged feedback”* (ANNE, 30 years old, Teacher III, City Central ES, City Division).

These statements show that teachers treat communication as part of research competence. They rehearse answers, anticipate questions, and build student confidence. They do not limit their role to supervising experiments. They train students to explain and defend their findings clearly.

This view is consistent with Tejero (2025), who emphasized that structured rehearsal strengthens students' confidence during science presentations. Moreover, Llano Jr. et al. (2023) highlighted that teacher mentoring includes guiding students in presenting and defending their work effectively. The teachers' experiences in this study reflect those findings.

Theme 4: Adapting to Time and Resource Constraints

Teachers speak openly about limited time and materials. One teacher stated, “*We eventually decided to work every Saturday*” (MARYJANE, 29 years old, Teacher I, Camambugan ES, Bohol Division). Another explained, “*I set a clear timeline... meet with them in their vacant times... frequent consultation*” (JEAN, 28 years old, Teacher I, Mansasa ES, City Division). She also mentioned adjusting procedures and borrowing space when materials were unavailable.

These responses show that teachers adjust when conditions are not ideal. They plan carefully, extend work hours, and modify methods when necessary. Their competence includes flexibility and practical problem-solving.

This aligns with Pasaquian (2024), who emphasized that teachers’ engagement in public elementary schools in the Philippines is closely tied to their ability to adapt, particularly in contexts where institutional resources are limited. In addition, Nguyen and Tran (2024) pointed out that sustained technical and structural support is necessary for teachers to manage research implementation challenges effectively. The teachers’ strategies in this study reflect those realities.

Theme 5: Learning Through Facilitation Experience

Teachers also describe growth through experience. One participant said, “*As a first timer... na pressure... nag research-research...*” (MARY, 27 years old, Teacher I, Larapan ES, Bohol Division). Another stated, “*Pareha pud mi nga ga learn*” (JEAN, 28 years old, Teacher I, Mansasa ES, City Division). A teacher described the experience as “*challenging and fulfilling*” (MARYJANE, 29 years old, Teacher I, Camambugan ES, Bohol Division).

These responses show that competence develops over time. Teachers feel pressure at first. They search for references and learn alongside students. Through experience, they gain confidence and improve their facilitation skills.

This interpretation is supported by Abelilla (2024), who explained that reflective practice strengthens teachers’ ability to handle SIP facilitation. Likewise, Schön’s theory of reflective practice emphasizes that professional growth occurs through reflection during and after action. The teachers’ accounts of learning through experience align with these perspectives.

In general, across both Bohol and City Divisions, teachers show similar core competencies in facilitating Science Investigatory Projects. In both areas, teachers guide students step by step, help them form clear research questions, design simple experiments, organize data through tables and graphs, and prepare for presentation. They also train students to answer possible questions and build confidence before contests. These accounts show that teachers in both divisions focus on clear instruction,

close supervision, and steady guidance throughout the research process. Their descriptions center on what they do directly with students inside and outside class time.

However, their emphasis differs slightly. Teachers in the Bohol Division often describe pressure, weekend work, and learning through experience, especially among first-time advisers. Their accounts highlight adjustment and personal effort. Teachers in the City Division speak more about timelines, structured meetings, and organized feedback sessions. Their descriptions focus on planning and method review. Even so, both divisions face similar limits in time and materials. Teachers respond by adjusting schedules, modifying procedures, and finding practical solutions. Overall, the data show shared competencies across divisions, with differences in emphasis rather than in skill.

The Influence of Administrators' Support and Teachers' Competence on Students' Proficiency in SIP

The analysis of the transcript generated four (4) themes that explain how administrators' support and teachers' competence influence student outcomes in Science Investigatory Projects. The findings show that support and guidance contribute to students' confidence development, growth in critical thinking and inquiry skills, improvement in research and communication abilities, and the development of independence and academic motivation. These themes are drawn from learners' accounts in both the Bohol and City Divisions and reflect how institutional and instructional support shape students' proficiency in SIP participation.

Theme 1: Confidence Development Through Support and Mentoring

Learners consistently identify confidence as a major outcome of the support they received. One learner shared, *"It has helped me deeply for they have motivated me in my journey, encouraged me, and given my team confidence"* (JOEL, 11 years old, Grade 6, Talibon ES, Bohol Division). Another stated, *"Nitabang sila naho sa pag increase sa ahong confidence"* (MARIE, 11 years old, Grade 6, Larapan ES, Bohol Division). In the City Division, a learner explained, *"I have learn the skill of not having stage fright... I have changed and learn how to be more brave on the stage"* (JHONNY, 11 years old, Grade 6, Mansasa ES, City Division).

These responses show that emotional support, rehearsal, and guidance directly affect students' self-confidence. Students connect their courage and reduced fear with the consistent encouragement and preparation provided by teachers and administrators.

Similarly, Tejero (2025) found that structured mentoring and guided rehearsal increase students' confidence during research presentations. Llano Jr. et al. (2023) also emphasized that teacher facilitation plays a key role in strengthening learner self-belief during investigatory work.

Theme 2: Growth in Critical Thinking and Inquiry Skills

Students describe clear improvements in thinking and inquiry skills. One learner stated, *“My critical thinking improved as I had to analyze data, question results, and look for reliable evidence”* (JOEL, 11 years old, Grade 6, Talibon ES, Bohol Division). Another shared, *“Participating in SIP has improved my confidence in conducting research, strengthened my critical thinking, and deepened my understanding of inquiry”* (JOSEPH, 11 years old, Grade 6, Camambugan ES, Bohol Division). In the City Division, a learner explained, *“It helped me with thinking quickly due to its time”* (JHONNY, 11 years old, Grade 6, Mansasa ES, City Division).

These statements show that students develop stronger analytical skills through participation. They mention analyzing results, answering quickly under time pressure, and understanding inquiry more deeply. The experience of defending findings and responding to questions sharpens their reasoning.

This theme aligns with Sanchez and Rosaroso (2019), who explained that structured mentoring in SIP strengthens analytical thinking. Tejero (2025) likewise noted that hands-on research improves inquiry and problem-solving skills.

Theme 3: Improvement in Research and Communication Skills

Learners also report gains in research writing and communication. One student said, *“I improved my research skills, writing and communication skills and time management”* (JOEL, 11 years old, Grade 6, Talibon ES, Bohol Division). Another explained, *“The support from my administrators and teacher is that they give us the things that we need... and also the advices on what to do and how to answer the questions”* (ANGEL, 12 years old, Grade 6, City Central ES, City Division). A City learner added, *“They practiced me to answer properly and using correct grammar in English”* (JHONNY, 11 years old, Grade 6, Mansasa ES, City Division).

These responses show that teacher competence influences students' ability to write, speak clearly, and answer questions confidently. Students link their improved communication directly to practice sessions and teacher advice.

Cai and Hong (2023) emphasized that teacher guidance in research processes strengthens students' research literacy. In addition, Llano Jr. et al. (2023) noted that structured facilitation improves students' ability to present scientific findings effectively.

Theme 4: Development of Independence and Academic Motivation

Some learners describe broader personal growth. One student said, *“Overall, SIP made me more independent, curious, and confident in solving problems and exploring new ideas”* (JOEL, 11 years old, Grade 6, Talibon ES, Bohol Division). Another shared, *“SIP Participation influenced me to develop my confidence and be not afraid to face the*

judges and it develops my love for research. I want to answer problems through research” (ANGEL, 12 years old, Grade 6, City Central ES, City Division).

These statements show that support and mentoring extend beyond skill development. Students express curiosity, independence, and interest in research. They describe wanting to solve problems through investigation.

Manalo (2021) found that sustained administrative and instructional support fosters long-term engagement in research programs. When students receive encouragement and recognition, their interest in scientific inquiry increases.

In essence, in the two divisions, learners report similar outcomes. They describe increased confidence, stronger critical thinking, improved research and communication skills, and greater motivation toward inquiry. Students clearly connect these outcomes to the guidance, encouragement, and structured preparation provided by teachers and administrators. Some emphasis differs slightly between divisions. City Division learners mention presentation practice, grammar, and contest preparation more often. Bohol Division learners focus more on confidence growth, curiosity, and independence. Despite these differences, the overall outcomes remain consistent. Administrative support and teacher competence together contribute to stronger student proficiency in Science Investigatory Projects.

DISCUSSION

This study sought to examine how administrators’ support, teachers’ competence, and student outcomes collectively shape the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects (SIP) in Bohol and City Divisions for School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, it aimed to identify the forms of support provided by school administrators, describe the competencies and experiences of science teachers in facilitating SIP, determine how administrative support and teacher competence influence student proficiency in research, and propose a research management framework based on the findings.

The study employed a qualitative research design using interview data from administrators, teachers, and student participants in both divisions. Data were gathered through semi-structured interviews and analyzed using reflexive thematic analysis. The analysis involved coding verbatim responses, clustering related codes, and constructing themes that reflected recurring meanings across participants. The approach allowed the study to examine how institutional support, instructional competence, and student experiences interact in the context of SIP implementation.

Findings

Based on the analyses conducted, the following are the salient findings of the study.

- 1. Forms of Administrative Support in SIP Implementation.** Analysis of the interview data identified six interrelated forms of administrative support that shape the implementation of Science Investigatory Projects: (1) Strategic Direction and Policy-Guided Implementation, (2) Resource Provision and Funding Mobilization, (3) Time and Structural Support for Project Work, (4) Implementation Oversight, Monitoring, and Accountability, (5) Human Resource Deployment and Capacity Building, and (6) Motivational and Recognition Support for Participation and Performance. Administrators establish clear guidelines, align SIP with institutional policies, allocate financial and material resources, adjust schedules to accommodate project demands, monitor progress, assign and mentor competent teachers, and provide recognition to sustain engagement.
- 2. Teachers' Competencies in Facilitating SIP.** The analysis further revealed five (5) core competencies that characterize teachers' roles in facilitating Science Investigatory Projects: (1) Scaffolding the Research Process, (2) Demonstrating Research Method Competence, (3) Coaching Scientific Communication, (4) Adapting to Time and Resource Constraints, and (5) Learning Through Facilitation Experience. Teachers guide students through structured research steps, assist in question formulation and experimental design, support data organization and presentation, prepare learners for defense, adjust to practical limitations, and develop professional competence through direct experience. These results show that effective SIP facilitation integrates instructional clarity, methodological knowledge, adaptive planning, and reflective growth.
- 3. The Influence of Administrators' Support and Teachers' Competence on Students' Proficiency in SIP.** Four key student outcomes emerged in relation to administrative support and teacher competence: (1) Confidence Development Through Support and Mentoring, (2) Growth in Critical Thinking and Inquiry Skills, (3) Improvement in Research and Communication Skills, and (4) Development of Independence and Academic Motivation. Learners reported increased confidence during presentations and defense, stronger analytical and inquiry abilities, improved research writing and communication skills, and greater curiosity and interest in solving problems through research. These outcomes indicate that student proficiency in SIP develops through structured institutional support combined with consistent instructional guidance.

Conclusions

Effective implementation of Science Investigatory Projects depends on clear administrative support, competent teacher guidance, and active student participation. Administrators provide direction, resources, time adjustments, monitoring, teacher support, and recognition. Teachers guide students step by step, assist in research design, train them for presentation, adjust to limits in time and materials, and improve through experience. Within this support system, students gain confidence, strengthen their critical thinking, improve research and communication skills, and develop greater independence

and interest in inquiry. SIP proficiency develops when leadership, teaching practices, and student effort work together in a structured and supportive environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen SIP implementation and support the key stakeholders involved:

1. The schools division superintendent must institutionalize clear and written SIP guidelines, structured timelines, and regular monitoring meetings to sustain strategic direction, oversight, and policy-aligned implementation across schools.
2. School heads and finance officers in public schools must allocate sufficient MOOE funds specifically for SIP materials and experimentation needs, and formalize partnerships with SPTA and community stakeholders to address funding gaps identified in both divisions.
3. Science teachers must engage in sustained professional development focused on research design, data organization, and scientific communication to strengthen methodological competence and structured mentoring practices.
4. SIP Coordinators and teachers must establish scheduled rehearsal sessions and consultation periods within the school calendar to systematically prepare students for presentation and defense, given the strong link between coaching and student confidence.
5. Public school supervisors and school heads must sustain recognition mechanisms such as school-level awarding, division representation, and public acknowledgment to reinforce motivation, independence, and continued interest in research participation.

PROPOSED RESEARCH MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

I. RATIONALE

Science Investigatory Projects serve as an essential platform for developing students' scientific thinking, research skills, and academic confidence. The findings of this study revealed that effective SIP implementation depends on structured administrative support, competent teacher facilitation, and sustained student engagement. However, variations in funding, time allocation, monitoring systems, and teacher preparation indicate the need for a structured management framework.

This Research Management Framework is proposed to institutionalize coordinated administrative action, strengthen teacher competence, and ensure consistent student research outcomes across schools in the Bohol and City Divisions.

II. SCOPE

This Research Management Framework shall apply to all public elementary and secondary schools implementing Science Investigatory Projects within the Bohol and City Divisions. It covers all stakeholders directly involved in the planning, supervision, facilitation, monitoring, and evaluation of SIP activities for the academic year.

Specifically, this framework shall apply to:

1. **School Heads and Administrators**, who are responsible for policy direction, resource allocation, supervision, and overall management of SIP implementation at the school level.
2. **Science Teachers and SIP Coordinators**, who facilitate the research process, mentor students, conduct consultations, and ensure adherence to methodological and ethical standards.
3. **Students participating in Science Investigatory Projects**, who are engaged in the conduct, documentation, and presentation of research projects under guided supervision.
4. **Division Education Program Supervisors in Science and Mathematics**, who provide technical guidance, monitoring support, and program oversight to ensure alignment with division standards and research objectives.

III. POLICY STATEMENT

This policy establishes a structured Research Management Framework to guide the effective implementation of Science Investigatory Projects (SIP) in schools within the Bohol and City Divisions. It ensures that SIP activities are supported through clear administrative direction, adequate resource allocation, systematic monitoring, strengthened teacher competence, and sustained student development outcomes. The policy promotes coordinated leadership and instructional practices to institutionalize research culture and improve student proficiency in scientific inquiry.

IV. POLICY GUIDELINES

To ensure effective implementation of Science Investigatory Projects, the following guidelines shall be observed:

A. Administrative Guidelines (School Heads and Administrators)

1. Establish clear written SIP guidelines, timelines, and procedural standards aligned with DepEd policies.
2. Allocate funds from MOOE specifically for SIP materials, experimentation needs, and competition participation.
3. Mobilize stakeholder support, including SPTA and community partners, when school funds are limited.

4. Adjust school schedules to provide structured time for research work, consultation, and rehearsal.
5. Conduct regular monitoring meetings to track project progress and address implementation gaps.
6. Assign competent Science teachers to spearhead SIP and provide access to professional development opportunities.
7. Institutionalize recognition mechanisms for outstanding SIP projects at the school level.

B. Instructional Guidelines (Science Teachers and SIP Coordinators)

1. Provide structured guidance in topic selection, research design, experimentation, data analysis, and documentation.
2. Conduct regular consultation sessions to ensure accuracy and methodological rigor.
3. Coach students in scientific writing, presentation skills, and defense preparation.
4. Maintain documentation of student progress and provide timely feedback.
5. Encourage originality, ethical research practices, and independent problem-solving.

C. Student Participation Guidelines (Students)

1. Follow approved research procedures and ethical standards in conducting experiments.
2. Participate actively in consultation sessions and scheduled rehearsals.
3. Ensure accuracy, honesty, and originality in research outputs.
4. Demonstrate responsibility in meeting timelines and documentation requirements.
5. Represent the school with professionalism in competitions and research forums.

V. FRAMEWORK COMPONENTS

Conceptual Framework

Figure 4. Integrated SIP Support and Development Framework

The framework consists of three interconnected components:

A. Administrative Support Structure (Supervisory Component)

School heads shall:

1. Provide clear SIP guidelines and timelines aligned with DepEd standards.
2. Allocate funds from MOOE and mobilize stakeholder support when necessary.
3. Restructure schedules to accommodate research work and coaching sessions.
4. Monitor project progress through regular follow-ups and documentation.
5. Assign competent teachers and support professional development.
6. Provide recognition and incentives for outstanding SIP outputs.

B. Teacher Facilitation Competence (Instructional Component)

Science teachers shall:

1. Guide students in topic selection, research design, experimentation, and data analysis.
2. Provide structured coaching in scientific writing and presentation.
3. Conduct regular consultation sessions and rehearsal defenses.
4. Adapt strategies when faced with resource or time constraints.
5. Encourage student independence while maintaining academic rigor.

C. Student Development Outcomes (Outcome Component)

Students are expected to demonstrate:

1. Improved research and science process skills.
2. Increased confidence in presenting and defending research.
3. Stronger critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.
4. Greater independence and responsibility in project completion.
5. Sustained motivation to participate in research competitions.

The proposed Integrated SIP Support and Development Framework illustrate SIP implementation as a structured and interrelated system composed of three core components: Administrative Support Structures, Teacher Facilitation Competence, and Student Development Outcomes. Administrative support provides the foundational conditions through strategic direction, resource allocation, time management, monitoring mechanisms, teacher capacity development, and recognition practices. These institutional structures enable teachers to operationalize SIP through guided research steps, methodological expertise, communication coaching, adaptive strategies, and reflective practice.

In turn, students demonstrate measurable outcomes in confidence, critical thinking, research and communication skills, and independence and motivation. The alignment in the framework emphasizes a sequential and interconnected process in which institutional leadership enables instructional practice, and instructional practice drives student growth.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION MECHANISM

1. Each school shall designate an SIP Coordinator to oversee implementation.
2. An annual SIP Implementation Plan shall be developed outlining timelines, budget allocation, monitoring schedule, and competition preparation.
3. Quarterly monitoring reports shall be submitted to the Division Office.
4. Professional development sessions for teachers shall be conducted at least once per academic year.
5. Recognition mechanisms shall be institutionalized at the school and division levels.

VII. MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Monitoring shall be conducted regularly at the school and division levels to ensure effective implementation of Science Investigatory Projects. It shall focus on the following key areas:

1. Presence and consistent implementation of structured SIP guidelines and timelines
2. Adequacy and proper utilization of allocated funds, materials, and laboratory resources

3. Regularity of consultation, mentoring, and rehearsal sessions conducted by teachers
4. Rate of student project completion and participation in school and division competitions
5. Observable improvement in the quality, organization, and presentation of student research outputs

An annual evaluation shall be undertaken to assess the overall effectiveness of administrative support mechanisms, teacher facilitation competence, and student research outcomes. The results of the evaluation shall serve as basis for policy refinement, resource planning, and capacity-building initiatives for the succeeding academic year.

VII. EXPECTED IMPACT

The adoption of this Research Management Framework is expected to:

1. Institutionalize systematic SIP implementation
2. Strengthen alignment between leadership and classroom practice
3. Improve student research proficiency and performance
4. Sustain a research-oriented school culture

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study observed the required ethical standards in the conduct of qualitative research. Prior to data collection, permission was secured from the appropriate school authorities, and informed consent was obtained from all adult participants. For student participants, parental consent and learner assent were secured before their inclusion in the study. Participants were informed of the purpose of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty.

Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained through the use of codes in place of participants' names and other identifying information. Interview recordings and transcripts were handled with care and used solely for research purposes. Throughout the study, the researcher upheld the principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice to ensure the protection, dignity, and welfare of all participants.

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